

CoreTrustSeal+FAIR-enabling

Capability Maturity Model

Supporting repositories' assessment of their capabilities and maturity in ways that align with Trustworthy Digital Repository (TDR) Requirements and the enabling of FAIR Data.

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Executive Summary

The *CoreTrustSeal+FAIRenabling Capability Maturity (CapMat)* model aligns the CoreTrustSeal Requirements with the FAIR Data Principles, allowing repositories to self-assess their practice and associated evidence with a view to their development and improvement.

The FAIR Data Principles define the expectation that digital objects should be findable, accessible, interoperable and re-usable. Repositories provide the organisational context for enabling FAIR digital objects. Trustworthy digital repositories (TDR), such as those certified to the CoreTrustSeal, offer long-term digital preservation services that can ensure digital assets remain FAIR over time. This text describes the alignment between the 15 FAIR Principles and the 16 CoreTrustSeal Requirements so that repositories can self-assess their trustworthiness and FAIR enabling status together. The associated capability-maturity model measures the repository in terms of the policies and procedures in place to demonstrate compliant practice.

FAIR enabling trustworthy digital repositories are acknowledged as key nodes in the research lifecycle and in networks of federated data infrastructures, including the European Open Science Cloud (EOSC). The community development of indicators, metrics and automated systems for assessing compliance with the FAIR Principles is ongoing and to date, no formal standard, process and governance structure is in place to certify FAIR objects or FAIR enabling repositories. The *CoreTrustSeal+FAIRenabling CapMat* self-assessment can be used immediately by repositories seeking to identify current levels of capability and to plan for increased maturity. Applying this approach supports the readiness of a repository for formal CoreTrustSeal certification. Other types of data and metadata service can also use it to prepare for future assessments of FAIR enabling capability.

Development of the *CoreTrustSeal+FAIRenabling CapMat* model has been iterated through engaged and informed public feedback.

This paper presents guidance for those applying the *CoreTrustSeal+FAIRenabling CapMat* model and provides detailed alignment of the CoreTrustSeal Requirements, FAIR Principles and Capability-Maturity levels.

Introduction

Repositories are acknowledged as vital nodes in the network of federated digital object infrastructures. Improvements in the provision of FAIR enabling trustworthy repositories have immediate benefits for the full research lifecycle. A number of project outcomes and reports liken the process of achieving both *Trust* and *FAIR* to a journey¹. This ongoing journey towards achieving FAIR digital objects in FAIR enabling TDRs is the key challenge to delivering a unified, formal certification standard and process. Ongoing improvement of digital objects and the repositories that care for them are necessary to meet these evolving expectations. There is a practical awareness that formal FAIR-related certification (of objects and/or repositories) should not be a 'gatekeeper' to engagement with the European Open Science Cloud (EOSC²). However, as noted by the EOSC Rules of Participation³: "though there is currently no single authority responsible for determining FAIRness, and no single threshold of data quality will be mandated across EOSC, openness of processes and responsibilities, together with transparency of decision making, is to be expected."

The content presented here can be applied immediately by repositories seeking to demonstrate their trustworthiness and FAIR enabling practice. It can also provide valuable insights to a wider range of digital object services, infrastructure providers, funding bodies and policy makers seeking to define, evaluate and reward FAIR enabling practices that ensure digital objects remain FAIR in the long term. Providing ongoing support to a range of digital object services, including repositories, will be the key to success.

The work to date has been informed by a wide range of source materials, including the *Turning FAIR into Reality* report⁴ which underlined the critical role of TDRs⁵ in ensuring the adoption and growth of the FAIR Data Principles⁶. Examples of TDRs include repositories certified to the CoreTrustSeal⁷ Requirements⁸. The RDA FAIR Data Maturity Model Working Group⁹ final

¹ E.g. Recommendations on certifying services required to enable FAIR within EOSC, Genova, F.(editor), Publications Office, 2021, <https://data.europa.eu/doi/10.2777/127253>

² <https://eosc.eu/>

³ European Commission, Directorate-General for Research and Innovation, EOSC rules of participation, Publications Office, 2021, <https://data.europa.eu/doi/10.2777/30541>

⁴ TFIR: European Commission (2018) Turning FAIR into Reality: Final Report and Action Plan from the European Commission Expert Group on FAIR Data. <https://doi.org/10.2777/1524>

⁵ Specifically TFIR Recommendations: Rec. 9: Develop assessment frameworks to certify FAIR services, Rec. 13: Develop metrics to certify FAIR services, Rec. 20: Deposit in Trusted Digital Repositories.

⁶ The FAIR Guiding Principles for scientific data management and stewardship <https://doi.org/10.1038/sdata.2016.18>

⁷ <https://www.coretrustseal.org>

⁸ CoreTrustSeal Standards and Certification Board. (2022). CoreTrustSeal Trustworthy Digital Repositories Requirements 2023-2025 Extended Guidance (V01.00). Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7051096>

⁹ <https://www.rd-alliance.org/groups/fair-data-maturity-model-wg>

report¹⁰ defines more specific indicators to enable the development of assessable FAIR metrics against which testing systems can be developed. One such system is the F-UJI tool¹¹. Work on these indicators, metrics and tests demonstrates that the evaluation of individual digital objects for FAIRness is dependent on an understanding of their environmental context (e.g. the repository that cares for them).

The capability-maturity levels and the associated community engagement tiers (used for Requirement 06: Expert Guidance) were the result of an initial FAIRsFAIR project design¹² and engagement with Science Europe work on maturity matrices¹³.

The term 'FAIR enabling' is used for the steps taken by repositories to ensure that digital objects become and remain FAIR. The critical function of a TDR is the provision of long-term digital preservation (LTDP) for a designated community¹⁴ of users. A TDR ensures technical continuity through file format migration or emulation, and maintains data and metadata so that they remain understandable to their community of users¹⁵. Together these steps ensure digital objects remain FAIR over time.

The *CoreTrustSeal+FAIRenabling CapMat* approach has benefited from multiple iterations¹⁶ of public feedback from the wider repository community, from the FAIRsFAIR supported repositories¹⁷ and through repository support carried out on other EOSC projects^{18,19}. The CoreTrustSeal Board has publicly expressed their support²⁰, though any changes to the CoreTrustSeal standard and process are dependent on their periodic community revision of requirements.

Methodology

In the context of evolving standards, digital objects and repository practice, it is critically important that repositories are able to self-assess their current capabilities and overall

¹⁰ FAIR Data Maturity Model Working Group (2020): *FAIR Data Maturity Model. Specification and Guidelines*. <https://doi.org/10.15497/rda00050>

¹¹ <https://www.fairsfair.eu/f-uji-automated-fair-data-assessment-tool>

¹² Capability Maturity & Community Engagement Design Statement <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4705235>

¹³ <https://scienceeurope.org/our-resources/practical-guide-to-sustainable-research-data/>

¹⁴ 'Designated Community' as defined by the *OAIS Reference Model* <https://public.ccsds.org/Pubs/650x0m2.pdf> and adopted by the *CoreTrustSeal Glossary* <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.3632563>

¹⁵ Explored in depth in the *FAIR+Time: Preservation for a Designated Community* Paper <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.5797776>

¹⁶ See Change Log at the end of the document

¹⁷ <https://www.fairsfair.eu/application-results-open-call-data-repositories>

¹⁸ SSHOC D8.2 Certification plan for SSHOC repositories, <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4558303>

¹⁹ EOSC-Nordic D4.1 An assessment of FAIR-uptake among regional digital repositories <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4045402>

²⁰ <https://www.coretrustseal.org/why-certification/coretrustsealfair-statement-of-cooperation-support/>

maturity status as part of planning a journey towards improvement. Capability-maturity models²¹, such as CMMI²², help organisations monitor their current status and plan for future progress in different ‘areas of focus’.

In this model the areas of focus being assessed for capability-maturity at the aligned requirements and principles of CoreTrustSeal+FAIR (See diagram 3 below)²³. Repositories self-assess their capability for each area at one of 5 levels: initial (1), managed (2), defined (3), quantitatively managed (4), and optimising (5). A capability at level **2. managed** for each requirement is proposed as the minimum expectation for CoreTrustSeal compliance.

Once a repository is achieving ‘defined’ (level 3) levels of *capability* across the requirements, it becomes more meaningful to refer to overall organisational *maturity*. ‘Defined’ implies that policy and practice are integrated and maintained across the wider organisation; from here the repository can progress to focus on ‘quantitative management’ (numerically/data-driven measurements and controls) and may progress to ‘optimising’ for continuous improvement.

Many of the CoreTrustSeal Requirements, under the headings of organisational infrastructure, digital object management and technology/security, are essential to FAIR enabling and there are multiple possible alignments between the CTS Requirements and FAIR Principles. The *CoreTrustSeal+FAIRenabling CapMat* provides a single *Requirement-to-Principle* mapping to assist repositories in assessing their current FAIR enabling status, alongside their overall TDR capability-maturity. This aligns with the CoreTrustSeal review process that seeks clear self-assessment statements supported by links to (ideally public) evidence.

The capability levels for each united ‘area of focus’ (Requirement and mapped Principle) address the repository’s ability to provide supporting evidence (policies, standard procedure etc.) that demonstrate compliant practice.

CoreTrustSeal+FAIRenabling CapMat is immediately applicable to repositories seeking to be both trustworthy and FAIR enabling. The remainder of this document presents the CoreTrustSeal Requirements to FAIR Principles alignment and their associated capability maturity levels, preceded by implementation guidance. This is followed by some concluding thoughts on the current and future status of the work, including sustainability and ongoing change management. Appendices provide a change log of the steps taken to reach this point and a supporting bibliography.

²¹ For an overview of current repository Capability-Maturity models, see CoreTrustSeal+FAIR Landscape of Capability Maturity Modeling - A FAIRsFAIR Discussion Paper <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.3862587>

²² Capability Maturity Model Integration (CMMI) Levels of Capability and Performance, <https://cmmiinstitute.com/learning/appraisals/levels>

²³ Explored in detail by Evaluation of Current CoreTrustSeal Guidelines and Extended Guidance to Consider their Implications for Maturity Modelling (FAIRsFAIR M4.1) <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.3735030>

CoreTrustSeal+FAIRenabling Capability Maturity

Implementation Guide

To ensure that the value of digital assets is maintained, it is desirable that TDRs enable the deposit, curation and preservation of digital objects that are FAIR for the long term. The CoreTrustSeal provides our reference for TDR standards:

Diagram 1: CoreTrustSeal Requirements

The primary reference for CoreTrustSeal is the Extended Guidance²⁴ document (currently at version 2.0), this should be used alongside the CoreTrustSeal Glossary²⁵.

All of the CoreTrustSeal Requirements are necessary to achieve TDR status. Though many of the CoreTrustSeal Requirements contribute to enabling FAIR digital objects, each FAIR Principle is aligned with a single CoreTrustSeal Requirement to streamline the preparation of self-assessment statements and supporting evidence.

²⁴CoreTrustSeal Trustworthy Digital Repositories Requirements 2023-2025 Extended Guidance (V01.00). <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7051096>

²⁵ CoreTrustSeal Trustworthy Data Repositories Requirements: Glossary 2023-2025 (V01.00). <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7051125>

Diagram 2 below presents mappings from the FAIR Principles to the CoreTrustSeal Requirements. A diagram presenting the converse CoreTrustSeal to FAIR mapping is included in Appendix 1 and parts of that diagram are presented under the subsections *Organisational Infrastructure*, *Digital Object Management*, and *Technology* below. Together these provide all the context necessary for a repository to self-assess as a FAIR enabling CoreTrustSeal TDR.

Diagram 2: FAIR Principles to CoreTrustSeal Alignment

The capability-maturity levels provided allow repositories to assess their current status and to plan for, and monitor progress towards, being FAIR enabling TDRs.

Demonstrating compliance with standards depends on a framework of policies, procedures and other business information in different areas of focus. The first three levels of the *CoreTrustSeal+FAIRenabling CapMat* are built around the preparation and implementation of appropriate evidence as follows²⁶:

1. Initial	Aware of the scope and issue within the area of focus (Requirement/Principle). Lists of all items relevant to the area of focus exist.
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²⁶ See Appendix 1: Capability-Maturity and Community Engagement Descriptions, for formal definitions.

2. Managed	Processes, procedures and other implementation measures are in place for all items on the lists.
3. Defined	Managed areas of focus (Requirement/Principle) are further integrated and maintained at the wider organisational level (policy and practice).

The authors' recommendation is that a capability level of **2. Managed** across all Requirements should be sufficient to demonstrate CoreTrustSeal compliance and FAIR enabling. Neither the CoreTrustSeal, nor the FAIR Principles specify a need for evidence of practice to be integrated and maintained at the wider organisational level (**3. Defined**). Note that CoreTrustSeal always prefers publicly available evidence to support self-assessment statements. Evidence may be made public at any level of capability-maturity, but we would suggest that assigning a **3. Defined** level should depend on making appropriately managed documentation (evidence) publicly available. Once compliance with Requirements/Principles reaches a capability level of **3. Defined** it becomes more meaningful to talk about the overall maturity of an organisation or service. Further progress can be made by achieving level **4. Quantitatively Managed** or **5. Optimising**.

Diagram 3: How *capability* within areas of focus can combine into overall *maturity*

Self-Assessment at Levels 4. *Quantitatively Managed* and 5. *Optimising*

Once repositories reach level **2. Defined** practice across the Requirements and Principles they may choose to seek higher levels of capability and maturity in one or more areas of focus. The details of reaching and maintaining these more challenging levels will differ between repositories, but there are some generally applicable considerations and some specific issues related to CoreTrustSeal Requirements.

Some methodology for 'counting' performance (level **4. Quantitatively Managed**) is a dependency if repositories want to periodically review their progress with a view to reaching level **5. Optimising**. Risks to repositories and the digital objects they care for are of course minimised with continuous improvement (**5. Optimising**) but quantitative management has an administrative overhead and repositories may choose to prioritise the areas they want to measure and optimise. In the context of FAIR and CoreTrustSeal, some areas of continuous improvement will be delivered through regular reviews, identification of community needs and timely updates to new standards.

For a mission & scope statement (R01) to be level **4. Quantitatively Managed** it would need to be linked to functions and activities that ensure it is delivered to defined levels e.g. KPIs (Key Performance Indicators). These would permit progress to level **5. Optimising**.

Quantitative management and optimisation for R02. Licences would be more practical if rights were described using a structured or machine-actionable standard (e.g. Open Digital Rights Language-ODRL²⁷).

Quantitative management of organisational infrastructure (R05) would equate to monitoring of both time and costs against repository functions with metrics (e.g. KPIs) in place. **5. Optimising** would involve the continuous improvement of governance processes and resource management to maximise the quality of service and minimise costs.

Preservation planning (R09) is a wide topic that has dependencies in many other CoreTrustSeal Requirements. For this reason the proposed capability-maturity levels focus on preservation *actions*. The fact that preservation is the central focus of trustworthy repositories could suggest that 'defined' should be the minimum level necessary for CoreTrustSeal, though some repositories, particularly those that are hosted by larger organisations may find it hard to deliver preservation planning that is fully integrated with their wider organisational practice.

Ideally preservation planning would be both quantitatively managed (prioritisation based on quantified demand from the community and quantified risk from technology watch) and optimising (continuous improvement and agile responses to opportunity and the need for change).

But reaching this ideal of digital preservation partially depends on wider community agreement about minimum standards, and is likely to require targeted investment in repositories as part of research infrastructure uplift.

Similarly, quality (R11) is a challenging concept to define and apply without further context²⁸ and community consensus. Quality and quality assurance depend on the selection or development of appropriate standards (implied across CoreTrustSeal) and workflows (R12) to

²⁷ <https://www.w3.org/TR/odrl-model/>

²⁸ e.g. Bruce & Hillman (2004) [The Continuum of Metadata Quality: Defining, Expressing, Exploiting](#)

curate for, and check for expected levels of quality. **4. Quantitatively Managed** depends on an agreed scale and evaluation process for quality. **5. Optimising** depends on an active strategy to increase quality over time.

Repositories seeking to achieve higher levels of capability-maturity should apply their local contexts to the evaluation and contribute to wider community discussion about how a TDR should be quantitatively managed and aim to become optimising.

Capturing an Initial Self-Assessment of Capability-Maturity

Though CoreTrustSeal applications require completion of prose evidence statements with links to supporting evidence, an initial self-assessment of *CoreTrustSeal+FAIRenabling CapMat* should be completed in tabular form. This document is accompanied by a *FAIR enabling TDR CapMat Self-Assessment template*²⁹ using the following structure.

CoreTrustSeal Requirement	FAIR Principle	Evidence Links	CapMat Assessment Level	CapMat Target	Notes
R02					
etc.					

Figure 1: Example of *CoreTrustSeal+FAIRenabling CapMat* Self-Assessment Template

It is suggested that repositories approach the completion of this template by following the workflow below:

²⁹ FAIR-Enabling-TD-Repositories-CapMat-SelfAssess-Template <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10724060>

Diagram 4: Suggested Capability-Maturity Self-Assessment Workflow

- Identify expert colleagues and review the CoreTrustSeal Requirements and the +FAIRenabling alignment (below). You may choose to add additional team members including digital object managers, organisational administrators, and technical and security staff.
- Complete a first version of the template, assigning a CapMat level to each Requirement/Principle, and adding links to available documentation (internal or public) that could provide evidence.
 - R06 Expert Guidance assigns an additional level for *Community Engagement*.
- If evidence is not available, or sufficient, consider what CapMat level you wish to achieve and define the actions and timeframes. This could include policies to be defined, procedures to be documented, or internal documentation to be prepared for public access.
 - Once actions are complete, repeat the CapMat assessment for the Requirement and evaluate your progress.
- As CapMat levels reach the agreed target, begin to prepare self-assessment statements and evidence links for the CoreTrustSeal application.

Not all repositories will meet the required thresholds for compliance the first time they self-assess and self-assessment should be repeated after taking corrective action.

There is not yet a formal certification to confirm a TDR as FAIR enabling. By applying the *CoreTrustSeal+FAIRenabling CapMat* approach a repository can evaluate its current status, plan for improvement and monitor progress towards a CoreTrustSeal application and the enabling of the FAIR data principles in a single process. This has direct benefits for service delivery and therefore to depositors, users and funders, whether or not a repository chooses to progress to certification as a TDR.

Diagram 5: *CoreTrustSeal+FAIRenabling CapMat: 3 Level Simple View*

Subject to approval by the CoreTrustSeal board, the authors recommend a capability level of **2. Managed** across all Requirements and Principles should be sufficient to demonstrate CoreTrustSeal compliance and FAIR enabling. Levels of 3 and above are highly desirable, but not all repositories are in a position to influence integration of practice at the policy level. See diagram 6 below and Appendix 2 for levels 4-5.

Once compliance with Requirements/Principles reach capability levels of **3. Defined** it becomes more meaningful to talk about the overall maturity of an organisation or service. Some repositories will seek to continuously improve beyond the targets set by the CoreTrustSeal Requirements and FAIR Principles. Further progress can be made by achieving level **4. Quantitatively managed** or **5. Optimising**.

Diagram 6: *CoreTrustSeal+FAIRenabling. Levels 4 and 5*

CoreTrustSeal Requirement R06 on Expert Guidance incorporates factors related to community engagement³⁰, so an additional three level self-assessment is also proposed for this dimension of repository practice.

³⁰ See Appendix: Capability-Maturity and Community Engagement Descriptions, for formal definitions.

Diagram 7: Levels of Community Engagement (simple)

Further details are presented under R06, with formal definitions included in Appendix 1.

The subsections below are presented in the sequence of the CoreTrustSeal Requirements (see diagram 1 above) and structured as follows:

CoreTrustSeal Requirement Short Name & Identifier (Rnn)
Rnn. CoreTrustSeal Requirement Identifier and full text.

1. Initial	Guidance on reaching an <i>Initial</i> level of capability.
2. Managed	Guidance on reaching a <i>Managed</i> level of capability.
3. Defined	Guidance in reaching a <i>Defined</i> level of capability.

Principle: ‘Number and text of the FAIR Principle’ if there is a CoreTrustSeal to FAIR mapping.

+FAIRenabling: Comments and suggestions on how a repository may seek to extend its CoreTrustSeal-compliant practice to be explicitly FAIR enabling.

Figure 2: Example of Requirement and Capability Maturity Level Layout in the Proceeding Sections

Organisational Infrastructure

Diagram 8: CoreTrustSeal Organisational Infrastructure to FAIR Principle Mapping

Mission & Scope (R01)

R01. The repository has an explicit mission to provide access to and preserve digital objects.

The key concepts for a repository mission statement might include: *designated community, deposit, store, curate, preserve, access and reuse.*

1. Initial	Self-assessment statements and evidence reference the key concepts and demonstrate that they are important to the applicant.
2. Managed	A mission statement is in place incorporating locally relevant key concepts.
3. Defined	A formal mission statement exists as part of a policy framework that ensures it is aligned across repository practice. It is clear who approves the mission statement and how it is reviewed and revised over time.

Rights Management (R02)

R02. The repository maintains all applicable rights and monitors compliance.

1. Initial	Every digital object being curated is known and recorded. The repository is aware that a rights statement is required for each, potentially with different rights applying to different parts of the data and metadata.
2. Managed	Every digital object, and relevant part of a digital object, has clear rights associated with it; defining permissions, prohibitions and duties of

	depositors, repository and end users. These rights permit the repository to store, curate, preserve and provide access to the digital objects for the defined period of responsibility (including 'indefinite') whether or not the original depositor or other rights holders remain available.
3. Defined	Rights management is integrated with the wider policy and practice framework and is managed in line with internal and external changes that impact rights.

Principle: 'R1.1. (meta)data are released with a clear and accessible data usage license'

+FAIRenabling: All digital objects have metadata that includes rights information covering (meta)data reuse.

Continuity of Service (R03)

R03. The Repository has a plan to ensure ongoing access to and preservation of its data and metadata.

1. Initial	All of the organisational activities and functions are known, and how they apply to digital objects is understood. This level is sufficient to ensure day to day continuity of service.
2. Managed	Policies and procedures are in place for each function. These go beyond the day to day process definitions (R11). A managed level of 'continuity of service' considers how a disaster can be mitigated, minimised and recovered from. This level would permit a succession plan to be <i>developed</i> for handover of digital objects and related functions in the event that the repository ceased to function.
3. Defined	Business continuity and disaster recovery measures are integrated across the whole organisation. This level of capability is necessary for the successful <i>implementation</i> of a succession plan.

Succession Plans: Depending on local circumstances (host organisations, rights and other issues) developing a succession plan covering all repository functions that is formally agreed with a successor organisation³¹ may not be possible. Repositories that reach a level of **3. Defined** are in the best position to address the issue of succession if it becomes necessary (e.g. cessation of funding).

³¹Necessary to reach the CoreTrustSeal Compliance Level 4. 'fully implemented'

Legal & Ethical (R04)

R04. The repository ensures to the extent possible that data and metadata are created, curated, preserved, accessed and used in compliance with legal and ethical norms.

1. Initial	Repositories know and have access to all the relevant legislation and ethical policies and practices that apply to their digital objects and the activity and functions they undertake.
2. Managed	The characteristics of each digital object (e.g. contains sensitive data, access restricted to a geographic area) are associated with relevant legal and ethical standards. Activities and functions applied to those objects meet those legal and ethical standards.
3. Defined	Legal and ethical practice is integrated into a whole-organisation policy and procedural framework.

Governance & Resources (R05)

R05. The repository has adequate funding and sufficient numbers of staff managed through a clear system of governance to effectively carry out the mission.

1. Initial	The applicant is clear on what <i>they</i> are responsible for, when responsibility is with a host organisation (if present) and when responsibility is shared with a third party (NB: this is the minimum necessary for a clear 'insource/outsource' statement in CoreTrustSeal R0. Context). Staff names, job titles and role descriptions are known. Departmental names and descriptions are in place. Projects and groups are listed and their purposes and intended outcomes are known. Individual, departmental, project and group costs and budgets are known.
2. Managed	Any hierarchies and decision making workflows are documented. Organisational structure descriptions or diagrams exist. Human and financial resources are managed in line with relevant workloads and funding availability. Funding is sustainable and sufficient.
3. Defined	Governance and resources are managed across organisational policy and practice. Cross-sectional alignment is in place across repository curation, preservation, governance, technology and security.

Expertise & Guidance (R06)

R06. The repository adopts mechanisms to secure ongoing expertise, guidance and feedback-either in-house, or external.

This Requirement contains two areas for evaluation:

- That the expertise needed is understood and is sought externally (Capability Level)
- That the repository engages with the wider community in relevant areas of practice (Community Engagement tiers: adopter, practitioner, coordinator)

Levels of Internal and External Expertise

1. Initial	The repository has listed the knowledge, skills and expertise related to their digital objects and repository functions.
2. Managed	The organisation monitors and maintains processes and procedures, ensuring the appropriate internal knowledge skills and expertise remain available to deliver them. Defined relationships with external service or information providers are in place to provide relevant guidance and expertise.
3. Defined	Alignment of objects and functions with internal and external expertise is integrated into the wider organisational policy and practice. These include managed feedback from the designated community that is explicitly met with responses that address their evolving needs.

Diagram 9: Community Engagement Tiers

Levels of Community Engagement

Adopter	For each area of expertise, define how the repository monitors community practice and integrates it into local practice.
Practitioner	In addition to adoption, the repository also engages with the design , development , and review of community practice. Consults and collaborates widely.
Coordinator	The repository is an adopter and practitioner that also takes a community coordination and leadership role. Driving maintenance and updates of existing practice and identifying next steps for the development of policy and implementation standards. Actively communicating and promoting existing and emerging approaches to the immediately impacted communities and the wider digital object infrastructure landscape.

Repositories should seek to progress through adopter, practitioner and coordinator status in areas they prioritise and where they have appropriate expertise. 'Adopter' should be the minimum target for a CoreTrustSeal applicant. Increased community engagement increases confidence in the repository's overall CoreTrustSeal and FAIR enabling practice. These levels have been developed from the basis of the three community engagement levels provided in *Appendix: Capability-Maturity and Community Engagement Descriptions*. Key words in the diagram are from the Levels of Community Engagement above.

NB: this process asks the repository for a high-level self-assessment of *overall* Community Engagement in terms of practices related to FAIR enabling trustworthy repositories. If external engagement is a priority, a repository might choose to self-assess community engagement against some or all of the other Requirements.

Digital Object Management

Diagram 10: Digital Object Management Requirements to FAIR Principles

Provenance and Authenticity (R07)

R07. The repository guarantees the authenticity of the digital objects and provides provenance information.

Though presented together in *CoreTrustSeal v2.0* the concepts of integrity and authenticity are sufficiently distinct to require separate capability-maturity levels.

Integrity

1. Initial	Objects are subject to integrity checks at the point of deposit, transfer to archival storage and transfer to access. Stored objects are subject to periodic integrity checks.
2. Managed	Processes and procedures include defined integrity measures. Any functions where change is not specifically permitted are supported by assurance that unintended change is avoided.
3. Defined	Integrity measures are part of an overall policy and procedural framework that defines which actors and agents are responsible for ensuring integrity and this is assured through governance and technical measures.

Authenticity

1. Initial	The minimum amount of pre-repository digital object provenance information that is required by the designated community is available (cf: R08 Deposit & Appraisal). Permitted and required changes to the object made during repository custody are listed.
2. Managed	Changes made to objects by the repository, whether originals or copies, follow documented processes, and changes are recorded. A documented version system is in place. Relevant information is made available to end users. This depends on a rights framework being in place (R02) and actors and their roles being known (R05).
3. Defined	All changes are part of an overall policy and procedural framework that is enforced through governance and technical measures. Actions and outcomes are recorded in a defined degree of detail.

Principle: 'R1.2. (meta)data are associated with detailed provenance'

+FAIRenabling: Repository provides evidence that metadata includes provenance information about digital objects' creation, curation and preservation in line with the needs of the designated community. The FAIR Principles do not make specific reference to integrity, but requiring valid provenance implies that unintended changes should be avoided.

Deposit & Appraisal (R08)

R08. The repository accepts data and metadata based on defined criteria to ensure relevance and understandability for users.

1. Initial	The minimal, acceptable and ideal characteristics of digital objects to be accepted into the repository are known.
2. Managed	A selection and appraisal process is in place that checks each digital object that is considered for deposit. Preferred and acceptable file format lists and metadata standards/schemas exist. Minimum metadata and documentation at the point of deposit are defined. Any objects that fail to meet the acceptance criteria are rejected, or the reasons for exceptions are documented.
3. Defined	Appraisal and selection processes at the point of deposit are integrated into wider organisational policy and practice. Data management plans (DMP) are integrated at the point of deposit and appraisal outcomes feed into curation and preservation plans.

Preservation Plan (R09)

R09. The repository assumes responsibility for long-term preservation and manages this function in a planned and documented way.

1. Initial	Preferred and accepted deposit (R08), access (R14) and preservation file formats and metadata standards/schema are listed. Every (meta)data object in the repository is listed and their file format and metadata standards/schemas are known. Any minimum periods of retention (bit level assurance) are documented.
2. Managed	The curation and preservation levels of all digital objects are documented. The needs of the designated community and the wider technical dependencies (risks) for digital object are monitored and used to define and implement curation and preservation actions. Actions, including normalisation, migration, emulation and updates to metadata and documentation ensure (meta)data remain findable, accessible, interoperable and reusable in line with the needs of the designated community.

	Preservation actions are taken as soon as is practical, in response to or in advance of identified changes to circumstances. Any minimum periods of preservation are documented.
3. Defined	Preservation planning is integrated into the wider organisational policy and practice including governance, resourcing, expert guidance (with community engagement) and technical infrastructure.

Principle: A2. ‘Metadata are accessible, even when the data are no longer available’

+FAIRenabling: The repository preservation plan ensures that metadata is preserved even when an object is removed from the repository. Any exceptions are defined and documented.

CoreTrustSeal+FAIR and CapMat note: Principle A2 is an explicit requirement that metadata is retained and *preserved* after data is unavailable so it is mapped here to R09. However this is also associated with standard practice for persistent identifier management, so the ‘tombstoning’ of metadata records is included in the CapMat levels for R12 Data Discovery and Identification).

Quality Assurance (R10)

R10. The repository addresses technical quality and standards compliance, and ensures that sufficient information is available for end users to make quality-related evaluations.

1. Initial	The repository is aware of the quality expectations at the point of reuse (R14). Curation activities ensure that any quality levels not met at the point of deposit are addressed to meet reuse and preservation needs. The repository is aware of relevant standards and works to meet them.
2. Managed	The quality expectations of digital objects not met at the point of deposit are integrated into a curation plan. Curation and preservation actions take place against the defined standards. Quality assurance of standards compliance takes place and any exceptions are documented. The digital objects at the point of access either reach defined quality thresholds or reasons for not meeting quality standards are documented.
3. Defined	Standards selection and quality assurance measures are integrated into the wider organisational policy and practice.

Workflows (R11)

R11. Digital object management takes place according to defined workflows from deposit to access.

1. Initial	The repository has identified the processes in place for deposit, curation, preservation, archival storage, discovery and access.
2. Managed	Documented workflows exist for deposit, curation, preservation, archival storage, discovery and access. Curation and preservation actions take place in line with defined standards and a curation plan developed at the point of deposit.
3. Defined	Workflow design, management and change management are integrated into the wider organisational policy and practice.

Discovery & Identification (R12)

R12. The repository enables users to discover the digital objects and refer to them in a persistent way through proper citation.

Note: Though presented together in *CoreTrustSeal v2.0* the concepts of discovery and identification are sufficiently distinct to require separate capability-maturity levels and separate alignment with the FAIR Principles.

Discovery

1. Initial	The digital objects' data, metadata and documentation are structured and presented in a way that passively permits indexing and harvesting by resource discovery systems.
2. Managed	Standards compliance processes are in place to ensure that digital objects can be included in resource discovery systems suitable for the designated community. These may include local systems, 'pushing' metadata to third party systems and catalogues or providing standardised metadata that can be pulled or harvested by other systems (e.g. OAI-PMH). Processes, procedures and other implementation measures are in place for all items on the lists.
3. Defined	Discovery processes and systems are further integrated into the wider organisational policy and practice.

Principle: 'F2. data are described with rich metadata (defined by R1 below)'

+FAIRenabling: The repository provides evidence that resource discovery metadata is sufficient for their designated community of users.

Principle: 'F4. (meta)data are registered or indexed in a searchable resource'

+FAIRenabling: A disciplinary repository may be expected to provide information for both general purpose resource discovery systems (exposure for indexing by search engines, high level metadata such as Dublin Core or DataCite), and metadata to support their more specialist designated community of users.

Identification

1. Initial	Every (meta)data object in the repository is known and has its own identifier in place.
2. Managed	Every object identifier is globally unique and persists over time. Processes are in place to ensure that the identifier continues to resolve correctly over time and that a metadata record persists even if, for some reason, the digital object is no longer accessible.
3. Defined	Local practice aligns with community agreed minimal standards for designing and managing globally unique identifiers and resolution systems including minimal practice for ensuring persistence and handling 'tombstone' metadata records for objects that are no longer accessible.

Principle: "F1. (meta)data are assigned a globally unique and persistent identifier"

+FAIRenabling: All objects in the repository are persistently identified. Any exceptions are documented and explained, including a timetable for complete coverage of persistent identifiers.

Principle: 'F3. metadata clearly and explicitly include the identifier of the data it describes'

+FAIRenabling: The repository provides evidence that digital object metadata includes the identifiers of the associated data e.g. files or streams.

Reuse (R13)

R13. The repository enables reuse of the digital objects over time, ensuring that appropriate information is available to support understanding and use.

The ReUse Requirement of CoreTrustSeal assesses two broad areas:

1. The means by which the repository identifies and addresses the needs of the designated community.
2. The characteristics of the data and metadata in the digital objects that meet these needs.

1. Initial	The repository has a definition of its designated community and documents assumptions about that community's specific needs. The repository documents the formats, metadata standards and other requirements for representing (viewing, editing etc.) the (meta) data and is aware that these may need to be updated over time.
2. Managed	The repository actively engages with their designated community to identify their needs in terms of (meta)data usability. This 'community watch' activity is applied alongside a 'technology watch' function that monitors potential risks to the current (meta)data approaches used for digital objects including obsolescence and seeks equivalent or improved alternatives.
3. Defined	Monitoring and change related to continued reusability of digital objects is integrated into the wider organisational policy and practice.

Principle: '11. (meta)data use a formal, accessible, shared, and broadly applicable language for knowledge representation.'

+FAIRenabling: The repository describes the knowledge representation approaches (schemas, ontologies etc.) they use to ensure machine-actionable interoperability.

Principle: 'I2. (meta)data use vocabularies that follow FAIR principles'

+FAIRenabling: The repository describes the ontologies and vocabularies used to describe their data, and how these meet the needs of the designated community.

Principle: 'I3. (meta)data include qualified references to other (meta)data'

+FAIRenabling: The repository provides evidence that relevant supporting information is available, such as links to literature, other datasets and metadata records, and how these meet the needs of the designated community.

Principle: 'R1. meta(data) are richly described with a plurality of accurate and relevant attributes.'

+FAIRenabling: The repository describes how the metadata provided for digital objects meets the needs of the designated community.

Principle: 'R1.3. (meta)data meet domain-relevant community standards.'

+FAIRenabling: (as for I1) the repository describes the knowledge representation approaches (schemas, ontologies etc.) they use to ensure machine-actionable interoperability and how those meet the needs of the designated community.

Technology

Diagram 11: Technology Requirements to FAIR Principles

Storage & Integrity (R14)

R14. The repository applies documented processes to ensure data and metadata storage and integrity.

1. Initial	Storage locations and media for all digital objects are known through deposit, curation, archival storage, discovery and access (and re-use if mediated by the repository). All storage locations form part of a backup system with at least two copies in separate locations. Backup frequency is known for each location.
2. Managed	All storage media management follows processes, procedures and other implementation measures including management as part of overall information technology infrastructure and technical watch (R15). Storage media are monitored for capacity and failure and are subject to a periodic media refreshment plan. Storage media types are assessed for obsolescence.
3. Defined	Storage is integrated into an overall technical infrastructure management plan which is in turn integrated into the wider organisational policy and practice. Storage locations are assessed for disaster threats. Storage media types, location risks, numbers of copies and backup periodicity all meet a documented minimum threshold (e.g. NDSA levels of Preservation ³² for Storage).

Technical Infrastructure (R15)

R15. The repository is managed on well-supported operating systems and other core infrastructural software and hardware appropriate to the services it provides to its Designated Community.

1. Initial	Parts of technical systems are listed, issues with technical systems and responses to issues are listed.
2. Managed	Full Lists of components and services, lists of issues (bug fixes, change requests) and research and development projects are managed through processes, procedures and other implementation measures.
3. Defined	IT service management is integrated with overall repository, governance and resource management.

³² <https://ndsa.org/publications/levels-of-digital-preservation/>

Principle: 'A1. (meta)data are retrievable by their identifier using a standardized communications protocol'.

+FAIRenabling: The repository describes the communication standards and associated methods by which objects can be accessed.

Principle: 'A1.1 the protocol is open, free, and universally implementable'.

+FAIRenabling: (as for A1) the repository describes the method by which objects can be accessed and the degree to which they are open, free and universally implementable.

Security (R16)

R16. The repository protects the facility and its data, metadata, products, services, and users.

Security is a similarly broad area to technical infrastructure, and as noted above expectations would increase for repositories curating sensitive digital objects. In a similar approach to R15, the reverse engineering of minimal and ideal practice from more advanced security standards (e.g. ISO27001) may be the best approach to defining the 'core' and from there a set of capability-maturity levels.

1. Initial	The scope of security is defined, and any security issues and responses to issues are listed.
2. Managed	Potential threats to the repository and its digital objects, products, services, and users are analysed and risks assessed. Processes are in place to periodically review risk, to mitigate risks where possible and to minimise and respond to threats (whether malicious or through human error) to the IT infrastructure.
3. Defined	Information security management is integrated with overall repository, governance and resource management.

Principle: 'A1.2 the protocol allows for an authentication and authorization procedure, where necessary.'

+FAIRenabling: The repository defines their terms for applying authentication and authorisation and the protocol in place to apply access control.

Conclusion & Next Steps

Repositories offering long-term preservation are already familiar with the concepts behind the FAIR Data Principles and undertake many activities that enable them. The CoreTrustSeal Trustworthy Digital Repository Requirements 2023-2025 have been mapped and aligned with the FAIR Data Principles to support repository self-assessment of FAIR enabling capability. Mapping decisions were guided by reference to a number of additional sources including the RDA Indicators and the FAIRsFAIR metrics³³ as applied by the F-UJI tool³⁴.

The mappings align the repository characteristics necessary to achieve Trustworthy Digital Repository (TDR) status with those that demonstrate a TDR is enabling FAIR (meta)data. The capability maturity (CapMat) approach is designed to support a self-assessment of repository capability against each requirement/principle 'area of focus'. The model focuses on the provision of supporting evidence (required by the CoreTrustSeal to support self-assessment statements) and can be used to identify current readiness levels and set targets for progress. Achieving sufficient capability can provide an indicator of overall repository maturity. Though the subtleties of trustworthy repository requirements and FAIR indicators will continue to evolve, there is an immediate benefit to repositories applying this approach. The CapMat levels lead up to and beyond those sufficient to achieve CoreTrustSeal TDR status and to demonstrate FAIR enabling practice. Repositories using *CoreTrustSeal+FAIRenabling CapMat* should do so in conjunction with the CoreTrustSeal Extended Guidance. Self-assessment and evidence should always demonstrate that the needs of a defined designated community of (meta)data users are being met.

Repositories are acknowledged to be key nodes in the network of research infrastructure. Improvements in the provision of FAIR enabling trustworthy repositories have immediate benefits for the full lifecycle of research. The use of these approaches provides further validation and testing of the alignment between FAIR research (meta)data objects and FAIR enabling trustworthy repositories. It also provides a stable baseline and a clear exemplar for the expansion of requirements and assessments (possibly including certification) to a wider range of services (including e.g. metadata registries) and FAIR digital objects (such as semantic artefacts). This reflects the acknowledgement that the evaluation of digital objects is partially dependent on the evaluation of the repositories and other organisations that care for them.

³³ D4.5 Report on FAIR Data Assessment Toolset and Badging Scheme
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.5336159>

³⁴ <https://www.f-uji.net/>

The wider challenges for standardisation and evaluation of an interoperable EOSC have been previously covered by the authors³⁵.

There is, as yet, no single standard and process for assessing and certifying trustworthy digital repositories (TDR) that enable FAIR research (meta)data objects for the long term. However, one analysis³⁶ of approximately 8000 datasets across 31 repositories in Europe found that the application of the FAIR principles in general provides an implied measure of repository FAIR-enabling characteristics. This suggests that an improvement of FAIR-enabling practices in a repository can result in increased FAIRness of new or newly curated digital objects).

Further progress on defining FAIR assessment and practice at the general and disciplinary level could enable integration into the CoreTrustSeal certification process in the future. This could be based on submission of a repository self-assessment that demonstrated a CapMat of **2. Managed** for each Requirement with one or more aligned FAIR Principles. Repositories have a long history of TDR standards development^{37, 38, 39, 40}, and a track record of defining best practice standards⁴¹ and supporting organisation^{42, 43, 44}. The equivalent standards and associated governance bodies are only beginning to emerge for FAIR⁴⁵. FAIR object indicators, metrics and tests have not yet been extended to address the more specialist needs for FAIR enabling, such as that delivered by the disciplinary repositories, which are a significant proportion of CoreTrustSeal applicants. There has also been limited work to date on FAIR object evaluation across a whole repository collection. It is expected that in future the evaluation of objects in a collection would form part of an assessment of repository practice.

The authors of the FAIR Principles see machine actionability as a key goal, and this will doubtless be critical to the successful delivery of a federated and interoperable EOSC. Machine-actionable testing of objects or of repositories (e.g. via interrogation of

³⁵ FAIR Ecosystem Components: Vision, <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.3734273>

³⁶ European Research Data Landscape Study Report (deliverables 3.2, 4.2, 5.2). Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7351121>

³⁷ Core Trustworthy Data Repositories Requirements 2020–2022 Extended Guidance, Version 2.0: September 2019, <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.3638211>

³⁸ DIN 31644, 2012 Edition - Information and documentation - Criteria for trustworthy digital archives https://global.ihs.com/doc_detail.cfm?document_name=DIN%2031644&item_s_key=00585595

³⁹ Explanatory notes on the nestor Seal for Trustworthy Digital Archives, <http://d-nb.info/1047613859/34>

⁴⁰ ISO 16363:2012 - Space data and information transfer systems — Audit and certification of trustworthy digital repositories, <https://www.iso.org/standard/56510.html>

⁴¹ ISO 14721:2012 - Space data and information transfer systems — Open archival information system (OAIS) — Reference model, <https://www.iso.org/standard/57284.html>

⁴² Digital Preservation Coalition: Digital Preservation Handbook, <https://www.dpconline.org/handbook>

⁴³ Digital Curation Centre, Digital Curation Standards, <https://dcc.ac.uk/guidance/standards>

⁴⁴ Dutch Digital Heritage Network, Who we are <https://netwerkdigitaalerfgoed.nl/wie-wij-zijn/>

⁴⁵ E.g. Research Data Alliance FAIR Data Maturity Model Working Group, <https://www.rd-alliance.org/groups/fair-data-maturity-model-wg>

repository-declared metadata⁴⁶) depends on community agreement and defined practice so that assessments can be designed and implemented at scale.

Repositories may have extremely heterogeneous collections, with some objects falling short of desired criteria for some valid reason e.g. an older but high-value, high-demand digital object that is complex or costly to bring up to standard. At present a human-mediated assessment such as that offered by CoreTrustSeal is capable of more subtle judgments compared to an entirely machine-automated process. Repositories increasingly function through a series of complex relationships between partners, with the 'quality' of the digital objects they receive depending on other organisations during other research lifecycle phases. The wider adoption of more standardised and 'living' data management plans (DMP) will enable the flow of information between stakeholders and mitigate some of these issues.

The immediate implementation of the *CoreTrustSeal+FAIRenabling CapMat* by repositories will support the expansion of trustworthy digital repositories, while ensuring the FAIR Data Principles are addressed.

Repositories using the *CoreTrustSeal+FAIRenabling CapMat* model should seek to contribute to the wider community discussion, particularly on what it means for a trustworthy repository to be **4. Quantitatively Managed** and **5. Optimising** through continuous improvement.

The ongoing maintenance of FAIR maturity indicators must be aligned with the development and community adoption of metrics, tests and tools for the automated assessment of FAIR digital objects. In addition to informing the expectations of FAIR enabling practice, the resulting FAIR object assessments could provide the basis for profiling a repository collection and integrating the outcomes into repository evaluation.

The development of clear community standards is a dependency for delivering machine-actionable assessments of both the digital objects, and the repositories storing them. These will require widespread changes that may require targeted investment in repositories as part of a wider research infrastructure uplift.

Change Log

In this revision of the CoreTrustSeal+FAIR CapMat during the FAIR IMPACT project, alignments with FAIR have been updated to the latest version of the CoreTrustSeal (2023-25) with extensive edits to the original text to reflect changes over time.

The previous version (02.00) of the model and alignment were presented in:

⁴⁶ D4.7 Tools for finding and selecting certified repositories for researchers and other stakeholders <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6090418>

Hervé L'Hours, Maaïke Verburg, Jerry de Vries, Linas Cepinskas, Ilona von Stein, Robert Huber, Joy Davidson, Patricia Herterich, & Benjamin Mathers. (2022). Report on a maturity model towards FAIR data in FAIR repositories (D4.6) (V2.0). Zenodo.

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6699520>

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Appendix 1: Capability-Maturity and Community Engagement Descriptions⁴⁷

A separate text provides a design statement⁴⁸ for the FAIRsFAIR approach to levels of capability and maturity. This was developed to provide internal consistency in project work, in cooperation with discussions around the proposed Science Europe maturity matrices⁴⁹ and with a view to alignment with formal capability maturity models such as CMMI⁵⁰.

FAIRsFAIR CoreTrustSeal+FAIR enabling Capability-Maturity Definitions

Unless otherwise referenced quoted text is taken from the *FAIRsFAIR Capability/Maturity and Community Engagement Design Statement*⁵¹.

“Compatible but simplified FAIRsFAIR approach (based on the CMMI levels below). Each tier description is applied to the organisation, repository or service entity being evaluated:

1. **Initial.** May be incomplete and fall short of the intent of the area of focus. Aware of and addressing performance issues.
2. **Managed.** Limited but complete coverage that delivers the full intent of the area of focus. Although lacking full alignment with overall organisational standards and practice, Identifies and monitors performance objectives. Includes and builds on level 1.
3. **Defined.** Complete coverage that delivers the full intent of the area of focus and aligns with overall organisational standards and practice. Identifies and monitors performance objectives that expand alignment to the whole organisation.”

The following definitions are taken from CMMI 2.0⁵².

“**Level 4: Quantitatively Managed.** Measured and controlled. Organisation is data-driven with quantitative performance improvement objectives that are predictable and aligned to meet the needs of internal and external stakeholders.

Level 5: Optimising. Stable and flexible. Organisation is focused on continuous improvement and is built to pivot and respond to opportunity and change. The organisation’s stability provides a platform for agility and innovation.”

⁴⁷ Originally released in M4.3 CoreTrustSeal+FAIRenabling, Capability and Maturity

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.5346822>

⁴⁸ <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4705235>

⁴⁹ <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4769702>

⁵⁰ [Capability Maturity Model Integration \(CMMI\)](#)

⁵¹ <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4705235>

⁵² <https://cmminstitute.com/learning/appraisals/levels>

Diagram 11: levels 1-5

Community Engagement Definitions:

“Awareness: Monitors community practice and makes local practitioners aware of it.

Adoption: Also supports practitioners to embed community practice locally.

Collaboration: Also engages with the design, development and review of community practice. Consults and collaborates widely, potentially taking a community coordination and leadership role. Driving maintenance and updates of existing practice and identifying new areas for the development of policy and implementation standards. Actively communicating and promoting existing and emerging approaches to the immediately impacted communities and the wider data infrastructure landscape

Appendix 2: CoreTrustSeal Requirements to FAIR Principles Alignment Diagram⁵³

⁵³ Originally released in M4.3 CoreTrustSeal+FAIRenabling, Capability and Maturity, <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.5346822>

Bibliography

CoreTrustSeal Standards and Certification Board. (2022). CoreTrustSeal Trustworthy Digital Repositories Requirements 2023-2025 Extended Guidance (V01.00). Zenodo.

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7051096>

[ISO 16363:2012: Space data and information transfer systems — Audit and certification of trustworthy digital repositories](#)

Consultative Committee for Space Data and Information Transfer Systems

[Reference Model for an Open Archival Information System \(OAIS\): CCSDS 650.0-M-2](#)

Consultative Committee for Space Data and Information Transfer Systems

[The FAIR Guiding Principles for scientific data management and stewardship](#)

Authors: Mark D. Wilkinson; Michel Dumontier; Ijsbrand Jan Aalbersberg; Gabrielle Appleton; Myles Axton; Arie Baak, Niklas Blomberg; Jan-Willem Boiten; Luiz Bonino da Silva Santos; Philip E. Bourne; Jildau Bouwman; Anthony J. Brookes; Tim Clark; Mercè Crosas; Ingrid Dillo; Olivier Dumon; Scott Edmunds; Chris T. Evelo; Richard Finkers; Alejandra Gonzalez-Beltran; Alasdair J.G. Gray; Paul Groth; Carole Goble; Jeffrey S. Grethe; Jaap Heringa; Peter A.C 't Hoen; Rob Hooft; Tobias Kuhn; Ruben Kok; Joost Kok; Scott J. Lusher; Maryann E. Martone; Albert Mons; Abel L. Packer; Bengt Persson; Philippe Rocca-Serra; Marco Roos; Rene van Schaik; Susanna-Assunta Sansone; Erik Schultes; Thierry Sengstag; Ted Slater; George Strawn; Morris A. Swertz; Mark Thompson; Johan van der Lei; Erik van Mulligen; Jan Velterop; Andra Waagmeester; Peter Wittenburg; Katherine Wolstencroft; Jun Zhao; Barend Mons

<https://doi.org/10.1038/sdata.2016.18>

[nestor Seal for Trustworthy Digital Archives](#)

nestorSeal Board

[FAIR Data Maturity Model. Specification and Guidelines](#)

Research Data Alliance FAIR Data Maturity Model Working Group

<https://doi.org/10.15497/rda00050>

[The TRUST Principles for Digital Repositories](#)

Authors: Dawei Lin; Jonathan Crabtree; Ingrid Dillo; Robert R. Downs; Rorie Edmunds; David Giarretta; Marisa De Giusti; Hervé L'Hours; Wim Hugo; Reyna Jenkyns; Varsha Khodiyar;

Maryann E. Martone; Mustapha Mokrane; Vivek Navale; Jonathan Petters; Barbara Sierman; Dina V. Sokolova; Martina Stockhause; John Westbrook

<https://doi.org/10.1038/s41597-020-0486-7>

[CoreTrustSeal: Second Draft Consultation of the Recommendations on certifying the services required to enable FAIR research outputs within EOSC. Feedback](#)

CoreTrustSeal Standards & Certification Board

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4311785>

[Practical Guide to Sustainable Research Data - Maturity Matrices for Research Funding Organisations, Research Performing Organisations, and Research Data Infrastructures](#)

Science Europe

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4769703>

Abbreviations and Acronyms

CapMat	Capability and Maturity
DMP	Data Management Plan
EOSC	European Open Science Cloud
FAIR	Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, Reusable
LTDP	Long-Term Digital Preservation
RDA	Research Data Alliance
TDR	Trustworthy Digital Repository